

BIOACTIVE CERAMIC-POLYMER COMPOSITES FOR BONE REPLACEMENT

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SUMMARY: Bone, at the ultra-structural level, is a composite with mechanical properties that can be matched by man-made composites. It serves as the template for developing bone replacement materials. Research on biomaterials analogous to bone was started in the early 1980s by incorporating bioactive particles into biocompatible polymers to produce bone substitutes. Hydroxyapatite reinforced high density polyethylene (HA/HDPE) is one of such materials and has been successfully used in the human body. In this paper, the structure and mechanical properties of bone are firstly reviewed. The production, structure, properties of HA/HDPE composites are then presented. Their biological properties are discussed as well. Clinical applications of the composites are clearly shown. Using the same or similar manufacturing processes, other bioactive composites have also been developed for tissue substitution or regeneration.

KEYWORDS : hydroxyapatite, polyethylene, bioactive composites, manufacture, structure, properties, tissue substitutes

INTRODUCTION

Numerous materials have been used for bone substitution ever since plaster of Paris was tried for bone repair since the 19th century. In modern day orthopaedic surgery, metals such as stainless steel and titanium alloy and ceramics such as alumina and zirconia are common in a variety of implants and devices. However, these materials, having been developed originally for other purposes, are considerably stiffer than human bone. The modulus mismatch between an implant material and the host tissue can cause bone to resorb at the implant-bone interface, which leads to implant instability and hence eventual failure [1]. A long lasting bone replacement requires the establishment of a stable bone-implant interface, which necessitates the careful matching of the mechanical behaviour as well as properties of synthetic implant materials with the natural tissue [2]. Furthermore, bone replacement materials must withstand any anticipated physical loads imposed by body actions without substantial dimensional changes, catastrophic fracture, or failure due to impact, creep, or fatigue within their expected lifetime in the body.

It is now generally recognised that the best material for replacing a body tissue is the one that is similar, if not identical, to that tissue [3]. The advances in composite technology have led to the production of new composites that mimic the structure and match properties of human tissues [4]. These novel materials may overcome problems that have been encountered with the use of conventional implant materials.

STRUCTURE AND PROPERTIES OF BONE

Bone is the substantial unit of human skeletal system, which supports the body and its movement. Bone, as a natural tissue, has a complex structure in which several levels of organization, from macro- to micro-scale, can be identified [1]. Take a human long bone such as femur for an example (Figure 1). It consists of an outer load-bearing shell of cortical bone with a medullary cavity containing cancellous bone towards the bone ends. Cortical (or compact) bone as a material is anisotropic with osteons (also know as "Haversian systems")

being oriented parallel to the long axis of the bone and interspersed in regions of non-oriented bone (Figure 2). Each osteon (about 100 to 300 μm in diameter) has a central Haversian canal (20 to 40 μm in diameter) containing a blood vessel, which supplies the elements required for bone remodeling. The Haversian canal is surrounded by 4 to 20 concentrically arranged lamellae with each lamella being 3 to 7 μm thick. Each adjacent lamellar layer has a different orientation of collagen fibres. Circumscribing the outermost concentric lamella of the osteon is a narrow zone known as cement line, which contains calcified mucopolysaccharides and is devoid of collagen. The cement line is 1 to 2 μm thick and is the weakest part of bone. The densely packed concentric lamellae in osteons are composed of two major components: fibrous collagen, which is a natural polymer, and bone mineral. The mineral crystallites that human bone contains are structurally calcium-deficient, carbonate-substituted hydroxyapatite (HA). They are usually referred to as bone apatite, which normally has dimensions of 5nm \times 5nm \times 50nm with a rod-like (or sometimes plate-like) habit and is embedded in collagen fibres. In mature bone, bone apatite occupies about 50% of the total volume. The precise microstructural organization of bone is a function of age and varies between different bones and between different locations of the same bone. Two levels of composite structure are considered when developing bone substitutes: first, the bone apatite reinforced collagen forming individual lamella (on the nm to μm scale) and, second, osteon reinforced interstitial bone (on the μm to mm scale). It is the apatite-collagen composite at the microscopic level that provides the basis for producing bioceramic-polymer composites for bone replacement.

Figure 1 Structural organisation in a human long bone [1]

Figure 2 Schematic diagram showing the microstructure of a section of a long bone [5]

The mechanical behaviour of bone may be assessed on whole bones *in vivo*. But the results obtained are difficult to interpret due to irregular shapes of bones and the organizational hierarchy in bones. Normally, mechanical properties of bone (cortical or cancellous) are determined *in vitro* using standard or miniature specimens that conform to various standards originally designed for conventional materials such as metals and plastics. The conditions required to prepare and test dead bone specimens so as to give meaningful results representative of living bone have been well established. It is very important to maintain water content of bone for mechanical assessment as the behaviour of bone in the "wet" condition significantly differs from that of bone in a dry state (Figure 3). In the quasi-static testing condition, a tensile test of "wet" cortical bone at ambient temperature gives a stress-strain curve exhibiting a small viscoelastic component and culminating in brittle fracture at a total strain of 0.5-3.0%. As a result of orientation, location and age, cortical bone has a range of associated properties rather than a unique set of values (Table 1). Young's modulus of bone ranges between 7 and 30GPa. It can also be seen from Table 1 that bone is significantly less stiff than the various alloys and ceramics currently utilized as prosthetic materials, but is stiffer than biomedical polymers. Cortical bone fractures in a brittle fashion, with the ultimate tensile strength being 50 to 150MPa. It has been shown that fracture toughness, an important parameter for brittle solids, of bone is considerably lower than those of metallic implant materials. The structure and properties of cancellous (or spongy) bone are also well understood and documented [7].

Figure 3 Effect of drying on the behaviour of human cortical bone [6]

Table 1 Mechanical properties of bone and current implant materials

Material	E (GPa)	σ (MPa)	ϵ (%)	K_{IC} (MN m ^{-3/2})
Cortical bone	7-30	50-150	1-3	2-12
Cancellous bone	0.05-0.5	10-20	5-7	
Co-Cr alloys	230	900-1540	10-30	~100
Austenitic stainless steel	200	540-1000	6-70	~100
Ti-6Al-4V alloy	106	900	12.5	~80
Alumina	400	450	~0.5	~3
Hydroxyapatite	30-100	60-190		~1
Polyethylene	1	30	>300	

E : Young's modulus

σ : tensile strength (in the case of alumina: flexural strength)

ϵ : elongation at fracture

K_{IC} : fracture toughness

A good understanding of the structure and properties of bone gives structural features and provides the range for approximating mechanical compatibility that is required of a bone analogue material for an exact structural replacement of bone with a stabilized bone-implant interface. It is important to bear in mind, however, that bone is unlike any engineering material in that it can alter its properties and configuration in response to changes in mechanical demand.

HYDROXYAPATITE REINFORCED POLYETHYLENE COMPOSITES FOR BONE REPLACEMENT

As bone is an apatite-collagen composite material at the ultra-structural level, a polymer matrix composite containing a particulate, bioactive component appears a natural choice for substituting cortical bone. Bonfield *et al* pioneered the use of hydroxyapatite (HA) particles as the bioactive and strengthening phase in polymers to produce bone analogues [8]. Hydroxyapatite ($\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$) closely resembles bone apatite and exhibits excellent bioactivity. Polyethylene (PE) is a proven biocompatible polymer and hence widely used in orthopaedics. It is therefore natural to combine the two materials to produce a composite that mimics the structure and matches mechanical properties of cortical bone. The ductile polyethylene allows the incorporation of relatively high volume percentages of HA particles in the polymer matrix, which is essential for obtaining bioactivity of the composite. As no coupling agent is used, all components of the composites are biocompatible.

Manufacture

HA/HDPE composites containing up to 45vol% (i.e. 73wt%) of HA can be routinely made through standardised procedures [9, 10]. The process for manufacturing HA/HDPE composites is outlined in the flowchart below.

Figure 4 Process for manufacturing HA/HDPE composites

Both commercially available HA powders and particulate HA produced in-house have been used to produce HA/HDPE composites. Either a twin screw extruder [9] or an internal mixer [10] was used for compounding the materials efficiently. Powdering of compounded materials usually took place in a centrifugal mill at below -100°C . Compression or injection moulding can produce bulk materials for prostheses or some small medical devices. Composites plates as thick as 20mm could be made by compression moulding. These plates are voids-free, as was revealed by X-ray radiographs.

Rheological studies revealed that the incorporation of particulate HA into HDPE resulted in an increase in the viscosity of composites at their processing temperatures [11]. The presence of the HA particles restricted molecular mobility of HDPE under shear and hence resulted in higher viscosity. This increase in viscosity was more pronounced at low shear rates (Figure 5). With an increase in shear rate, the viscosity of HA/HDPE composites approached that of the unfilled HDPE. Both HDPE and HA/HDPE composites showed pronounced shear thinning behaviour. HA/HDPE composites at their processing temperatures exhibited discontinuity with a varying shear rate. As the HA content in the composites increased, the shear rates at which discontinuity occurred was reduced. The die swell ratio of HA/HDPE composites was reduced as the HA content was increased. It is possible that the presence of HA particles in the polymer matrix reduced the degree of recoiling of the HDPE molecular chains and hence led to the reduction in swelling of composites. Analysis of rheological behaviour of HA/HDPE composites is important for optimising composite processing conditions and for producing high quality net-shape (or near near-shape) devices.

Figure 5 Apparent viscosity vs. apparent shear rate for HA/HDPE composites at 190°C [11]

Structure

SEM examinations of polished HA/HDPE surfaces showed that after the compounding process, HA particles were well dispersed, exhibiting a homogeneous distribution in the polymer matrix (Figure 6). Subsequent composite processing by compression moulding preserved these characteristics. This uniform distribution of HA particles in composites is essential for mechanical as well as biological performance of implants. Using the image analysis technique and stereology, it was possible to calculate the average volume diameter of HA particles in composites from SEM micrographs (i.e., from two-dimensional images to three-dimensional projections). The calculations indicated that the high shear forces generated during the compounding process broke up HA particle agglomerates into unit particles in the polymer matrix [12]. The average volume diameter of HA particles in compounded HA/HDPE was nearly the same as the mean particle size of HA powder used for producing the composites. SEM examinations of tensile fracture surfaces suggested that in the composites there was only mechanical bond between HA particles and HDPE matrix resulting from the shrinkage of HDPE around individual HA particles during thermal processing [9, 13].

Figure 6 Uniform distribution of HA particles in HA/HDPE composite containing 40vol% of HA [9]

It was found that compounding caused slight decreases in the weight average molecular mass (M_w) of HDPE, with the decrease being dependent on the HA volume fraction [13]. Further thermal processing by compression or injection moulding also reduced M_w . Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) results indicated that the addition of HA particles caused decreases in the degree of crystallinity of HDPE, with composites of higher HA contents having lower degrees of crystallinity for the polymer matrix [10].

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was used to determine the real HA content in HA/HDPE composites. Calculations made from TGA curves showed that the difference between the actual mass percentages of HA in the composites produced and the “Rule of Mixtures (ROM)” values was negligible and hence the intended compositions had been achieved [10].

Mechanical Properties

By varying the amount of HA in the composites, a range of mechanical properties of the composites could be obtained. An increase in the HA volume percentage led to increases in the Young's modulus, shear modulus and tensile strength of HA/HDPE, with a corresponding decrease in the strain to fracture [9, 14]. The particle morphology and average particle size of HA were found to affect mechanical properties of HA/HDPE composites [14]. HA/HDPE with 45vol% of HA possessed a Young's modulus value of 5.54GPa, which approaches the lower bound for cortical bone (Table 2). HA/HDPE composites containing 40vol% or more of HA appeared to be suitable for bone substitution, with the actual composite to be used depending on the nature of bone being replaced and the applied physiological load.

Table 2 Mechanical properties of HA/HDPE composites

HA Volume (%)	E (GPa)	G (GPa)	σ (MPa)	ϵ (%)
0	0.65±0.02	0.28±0.10	17.89±0.29	>360
10	0.98±0.02	0.39±0.16	17.30±0.27	>200
20	1.60±0.02	0.48±0.07	17.77±0.09	34.0±9.5
30	2.73±0.10	0.71±0.17	19.55±0.20	6.4±0.5
40	4.29±0.17	1.18±0.07	20.67±1.56	2.6±0.4
45	5.54±0.62	1.46±0.26	18.98±2.11	1.9±0.2

E : Young's modulus G : shear modulus σ : tensile strength ϵ : elongation at fracture

Using an instrumented falling weight impact tester, it was shown that for HA/HDPE composites, an increase in HA content produced a decrease in impact energy for fracture [15]. Under this type of impact condition, the failure of composites containing various amounts of HA was classified as “brittle”, with no evidence of gross plastic deformation when compared to the rupture of the matrix polymer itself.

Microhardness of HA/HDPE composites increased with an increase in HA content [10, 16]. However, for a given volume fraction of the ceramic phase (either HA or bone apatite), the hardness of HA/HDPE composites was considerably lower than that of the natural tissue, which may be due to the different size and distribution of the ceramic phase and the way in which it is bound to the matrix.

Dynamical properties and the damping capability of HA/HDPE composites were also studied in detail [10, 13]. Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) showed that the storage modulus of the composites increased with the increase in HA content and decreased with the increase in temperature (Figure 7). Unlike storage modulus which increased monotonically with the increase in temperature, the loss modulus of the composites decreased with the temperature rise from -100°C to -25°C . It then increased to peak at around 40°C , with a subsequent decrease towards higher temperatures. It was shown that the addition of HA particles into HDPE reduced the damping (as indicated by $\tan \delta$ values in the DMA analysis) of the polymer, with the degree of reduction depending upon the HA volume fraction [13].

Figure 7 Variation of storage modulus with temperature for HA/HDPE composites [13]

The creep behaviour of HA/HDPE composites was investigated using a three-station tensile

creep machine [17, 18]. The inclusion of HA particles in HDPE improved the short-term creep resistance when specimens were subjected to similar stresses and an increase in the HA volume fraction increased creep resistance (Figure 8). However, creep failure of composites could occur at long times due to debonding at the HA-HDPE interface. The immersion in Ringer's solution reduced the creep resistance of HA/HDPE composites. The decrease in creep resistance was found to be a function of HA volume fraction [18]. This effect was due to the penetration of fluid into the composites.

Figure 8 Creep strain vs. time for HA/HDPE composites at different stress levels in Ringer's solution [17]

Biaxial (i.e., axial and torsional) fatigue tests were conducted for HA/HDPE composites [19]. The ultimate shear strength of HDPE and HA/HDPE composite with 20vol% of HA was determined to be 17.12 and 17.46MPa, respectively. A fixed axial component of 50% of ultimate tensile strength (UTS) with the torsional component varying from 0% to 50% of ultimate shear strength (USS) was used for fatigue tests. Generally, the fatigue life of HDPE and the composites was reduced with an increasing shear stress in the biaxial stress condition (Figure 9). The addition of particulate HA in HDPE led to shorter fatigue life in low shear stress conditions. In high shear stress conditions, the effects of shear stress became dominant and the fatigue life of both HDPE and HA/HDPE was about the same.

Figure 9 Fatigue life of HDPE and HA/HDPE under various biaxial fatigue stress conditions [19]

Tribological properties of HDPE and HA/HDPE composites were evaluated against duplex stainless steel under dry and lubricated conditions [20]. Lubricants included distilled water and aqueous solutions of proteins (egg albumen or glucose). It was found that HA/HDPE composites had lower coefficients of friction than HDPE under certain conditions. The addition of HA beyond 10vol% deteriorated the tribological properties of HA/HDPE composites by forming an abrasive slurry of HA in the lubricants. HA/HDPE composites appeared unsuitable for implants with articulating surfaces.

***In vitro* and *in vivo* Assessments**

The biological performance of implant materials can be evaluated by *in vitro* tests, using simulated body fluid or cell cultures, or by *in vivo* assessments. In *in vitro* experiments using human osteoblast cell primary cultures, it was observed that the osteoblast cells attached to

"islands" of HA in the composites and subsequent proliferated (Figure 10), which clearly showed the biocompatibility and bioactivity of HA/HDPE composites [21].

Figure 10 Human osteoblast cells attached to the surface of a HA/HDPE composite [21]

For *in vivo* experiments, following sterilization by γ irradiation, machined pins ($\Phi 2.4\text{mm} \times 5\text{mm}$) of HA/HDPE composites were implanted in the lateral femoral condyle of adult New Zealand white rabbits [22]. It was demonstrated that cortical and cancellous bones responded positively to the presence of HA/HDPE implant by localized apposition adjacent to the implant surface. After six month implantation, the areas of direct bone apposition, as measured from histological sections, had reached 40% of the implant surface. The mechanical compatibility of the HA/HDPE composite with natural bone had resulted in the absence of significant relative movement at the implant-bone interface, thus encouraging bone growth around the implant. Ultra-microtomed specimens were prepared for TEM examinations of the bone-implant interface [23]. At one month, the new bone was mainly seen adjacent to the interface where HA particles were present. At six months, the bone tissue was seen growing along the whole length of composite implant including exposed HA particles and polyethylene matrix. The image of lattice planes at the bone-implant interface after three months implantation is shown in Figure 11, exhibiting continuity across the interface and thus indicating epitaxial growth of apatite crystals from the implant.

Figure 11 High resolution TEM image of the bone-implant interface for a HA/HDPE implant [23]

Clinical Applications

Since the late 1980s, subperiosteal orbital floor implants made from HA/HDPE composites have been used in the correction of volume deficient sockets and in orbital floor reconstruction following trauma [24, 25]. All the implants remained in position and no infection or extrusion occurred. Clinical examination found the implants to feel stable. After six months implantation, computer tomography (CT) was unable to detect any gap between the implant and the bone, implying at least partial integration of the implant with the orbital floor, which accounted for the marked implant stability (Figure 12).

Figure 12 CT scan of orbits of a patient 24 month after operation [24]

More recently, middle ear implants are made from HA/HDPE composites and satisfactory clinical results have been obtained [26]. Figure 13 shows a middle ear implant that is commercially available since mid-1990s.

Figure 13 A middle ear implant made from HA/HDPE composite (The diameter of the implant shaft is 1.68mm.) [26]

BIOCERAMICS REINFORCED POLYMERS FOR TISSUE REPLACEMENT OR TISSUE REGENERATION

To improve mechanical properties of HA/HDPE composites for load bearing implant applications, hydrostatic extrusion was investigated [27]. It was found that higher extrusion ratios led to higher Young's modulus and tensile strength of HA/HDPE composites which are inside the bounds for mechanical properties of cortical bone. The fracture strain of HA/HDPE was also substantially increased by hydrostatic extrusion. Extruded HA/HDPE containing 40vol% of HA possessed a strain to fracture which was far greater than that of human cortical bone (9.4% vs. 1-3%). Furthermore, the bioactivity of the composites was retained after extrusion. Therefore, HA/HDPE further processed via hydrostatic extrusion exhibited great potential for major load bearing applications. An alternative method to enhance mechanical properties of the composites, i.e., using a coupling agent for the composites, was also studied [28]. However, only marginal improvements were achieved.

Apart from polyethylene, there are a few other biomedical polymers that could be used for producing bone analogue materials. Furthermore, to establish a stronger implant-bone interface within a shorter period of time, glass or ceramics that are more bioactive than HA, such as Bioglass® and AW glass-ceramic, can be used as the bioactive phase in composites. Therefore, using the same or similar manufacturing processes, other bioactive composites have also been developed for tissue substitution or regeneration [29-33]. Some of these new bioactive composites have been systematically investigated for potential medical applications.

The future development in tissue repair may also depend on research in the emerging field of tissue engineering. However, the traditional approach in designing new materials for specific applications will still remain as an essential and viable means in the course of combating problems in the medical field.

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